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Reading Comprehension and Academic Performance of Students

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Abstract

Reading comprehension is a fundamental skill that significantly influences students' academic success, particularly at the Senior High School level where academic tasks demand higher-order thinking skills. This study investigated the relationship between reading comprehension and academic performance of Grade 12 Senior High School students of San Miguel National High School, San Miguel, Bulacan, during School Year 2022–2023. The study employed a quantitative correlational research design involving 258 Grade 12 students selected through simple random sampling. A 40-item standardized reading comprehension test was used to measure students' reading comprehension levels, while academic performance was determined using the students' General Weighted Average (GWA).

Descriptive statistics, including frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation, were used to describe the students' demographic profile, reading comprehension levels, and academic performance. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was applied to determine the relationship between reading comprehension and academic performance. Results revealed that the respondents demonstrated a high level of reading comprehension and very high academic performance. Furthermore, findings indicated a weak but statistically significant positive relationship between reading comprehension and academic performance ($r = .355, p = .001$). The results suggest that improvements in students' reading comprehension are associated with better academic performance. Hence, strengthening reading comprehension through effective instructional strategies and school-wide literacy programs is recommended to further enhance students' academic achievement.

Keywords: Reading Comprehension; Academic Performance; Senior High School; Grade 12 Students; Correlational Study

1. Introduction

Today, the ability to read and write is on top of the priority. Teaching the students to be basically and functionally literate is indeed a must since the contemporary world demands that the learned should obtain more than the traditional literacy skill. The National Council of Teachers of English (NCTE, 2013) argues that a person living in the 21st century global society must be able to: be proficient and fluent in using the tools of technology; build intentional cross-cultural connection and relationship; design and share information for global communities; manage, analyze, and synthesize multiple streams of simultaneous information; and create, critique, analyze and evaluate multimedia texts. This, thus poses a more challenging task for teachers to produce globally competitive students who are 'multiliteracies'.

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Nevertheless, it is also noteworthy to look at the figures of literacy rate in the Philippines. In 2008, the Functional Literacy, Education and Mass Media Survey (FLEMMS) revealed that 95.6% of the total population is basically literate. This overwhelming increase in our rate clearly indicates a positive impact to the education landscape of the country and to economic development since the technology-driven world is rapidly changing. However, FLEMMS also noted that the number of individuals lacking in counting and comprehension skills grew which can be associated in the population growth of the country from 57.6 million in 2003 to 67 million for 2008. Consequently, Dr. Ricardo Ma. Nalasco, an education reform advocate, found advocates found it an important matter for the state to look into the details that 9.1 million Filipinos are non-numerate and 20.1 million individuals lack comprehension abilities.

With the given figures from the latest survey that the government has conducted, it is timely and current to give emphasis on the impact of reading comprehension to Filipinos to create a positive impact to the education landscape of the country and to economic development since the technology-driven world is rapidly changing.

Undoubtedly, reading is one of the most essential study skills in all levels of education. Establishing good reading has a huge impact on an individual. Through this, a reader can improve his/her focus and concentration, improve his/her verbal ability, kindle his/her imagination, elevate his/her intellectual capability, improve memory, and discover himself/herself.

Today, the Department of Education is implementing the K to 12 Program known as The Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum. The additional two years will be spent on the Senior High School education. This Senior High School program includes academic and even technical subjects. These subjects demand that students be able to comprehend what they read in order to succeed in their academic life. It will be noteworthy to check on the student's current reading comprehension skills and its relationship to their academic performance.

Reading process, in a sense, is to recognize sounds, syllables, words, and convert them into sounds it is a reporting process in a systematic form, in a gradual structure that textual components require one another such as sentence, word, syllable and sound. In another sense, the reading process is a reader's extrapolation process about sentences and words in the text by activating his background knowledge at a higher level in the direction of instructions of the text (Alderson, 2000; Treiman 2003).

Meanwhile, reading comprehension is a complex cognitive and interactive process of deriving meaning from a text (Rumelhart, 1981). In addition, Trehearne and Doctorow (2005) support this claim saying that it is an interaction of different variables (reader, text, environment) in a sociocultural context. It is viewed as a complex set of cognitive activities involving many skills and dimensions such as 'the perception of words, clear grasp of meaning, thoughtful reaction, and integration' (Hermosa, 2002).

This strengthens the need for Senior High School students to have an adequate ability to comprehend what they read in order to succeed in their endeavour. Al Noursi (2014) argues that the ability to read for various purposes is a precursor of a successful learning in schools, colleges, and universities. He adds that it is a survival skill in the 21st century may it be students or professionals.

On the other hand, reading motivation is the interest or desire to read different reasons or purposes. Positive reinforcements have favorable effects towards motivation in reading; hence, it is a must that teachers design motivating and engaging reading activities for learners to develop the real love and passion for reading (Hermosa, 2002). Baker, Dreher, and Gurthrie (2000) suggest that for students to be motivated to read, teachers and parents alike must provide children good foundation at the word level, serve as guide on the side, provide opportunities to read learn with sufficient interesting reading materials, create a sharing community of learners, make learning contexts stress-free and fun, identify specific child's strengths and weakness, provide ample time to read, coordinate with other teachers and administrators for a holistic reading program, partner with parents, learn the strategies for engaging and fruitful learning.

Certainly, if a student under the Senior High School Program is faced with challenging reading tasks, one must consider that reading involves both cognitive affective features (Guthrie & Wigfield, 2005). Students may be proficient at reading but they may be also reluctant to read. In other words, as Lau (2004) stated that many useful strategies with the purpose of improving students' reading skills could be taught to students. However, students will want to benefit from those strategies only if they are motivated for reading. This is the second dimension of reading as described by Server (1990) that motivation is regarded as the affective aspect of reading.

Duy (2007) defined motivation as the inner ability, a stimulus that pushes a person to act to achieve a goal. Motivation, which is by definition tripwire, multifaceted, and prompt in using mind and language that changes depending on time (Guthrie & Wigfield, 2000).

Given the context on the importance of reading comprehension and its relationship with reading motivation among Senior High School students, this study explores the correlation of the two variables.

Given the importance of reading comprehension in academic achievement, it is necessary to assess students' reading abilities and examine how these skills relate to their academic performance. This study focuses on determining the relationship between reading comprehension and academic performance of Grade 12 students of San Miguel National High School, San Miguel, Bulacan, during School Year 2022–2023.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

This study aims to determine the relationship between reading comprehension and academic performance of Grade 12 Senior High School students of San Miguel National High School, San Miguel, Bulacan.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

What is the demographic profile of the students in terms of:

- Age;
- Strand; and
- Gender?
- How may the level of students' reading comprehension be described?
- How may the academic performance of the students be described?
- Is there a significant relationship between students' reading comprehension and academic performance?

1.2. Hypothesis

Ho: There is no significant relationship between the reading comprehension and academic performance of Grade 12 students of San Miguel National High School.

1.3. Scope and Delimitation

This study focuses on determining the relationship between the reading comprehension level and academic performance of Grade 12 Senior High School students of San Miguel National High School, San Miguel, Bulacan, during School Year 2022–2023. The respondents consisted of 258 Grade 12 students selected through simple random sampling. Reading comprehension was measured using a standardized reading comprehension test, while academic performance was based on students' General Weighted Average (GWA). Other factors affecting academic performance were not included in the study.

2. Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored on the Schema Theory. This theory is an explanation of how readers use prior knowledge to comprehend and learn from text (Rumelhart, 1980). The term "schema" was first used in psychology by Barlett as "an active organization of past reactions or experiences" (1932, p.201), later schema was introduced in reading by Rumelhart (1980), Carell (1981) and Hudson (1982) when discussing the important role of background knowledge in reading comprehension (all cited in An,2013). The fundamental principle of the Schema Theory assumes that written text does not carry meaning by itself. Rather, a text only provides directions for readers as to how they should retrieve or construct meaning from their own previously acquired knowledge (An,2013).

According to Schema Theory, comprehending a text is an interactive process between the reader's background knowledge and the text. Efficient comprehension requires the ability to relate the textual material to one's own knowledge. As Anderson (1977, p.369) points out, "every act of comprehension involves one's knowledge of the world as well". Reading comprehension operates in two directions, from bottom up to the top and from the top down to the bottom of the hierarchy. Bottom-up processing is activated by specific data from the text, while top-down processing starts with general to confirm these predictions. These two kinds of processing are occurring simultaneously and interactively, which adds to the concept of interaction or comprehension between bottom-up and top-down processes (Carrel and Eiserhold,1983).

Also, this study echoes theory related to reading motivation since it plays an important role in reading. This is where the Self-efficacy Theory of Albert Bandura comes in. Albert Bandura (1986) suggests that motivation (or a lack thereof) is the result of an individual's self-efficacy as the beliefs we have about ourselves that cause us to make choices, put forth effort, and persist in the face of difficulty. And for help in the classroom, Bandura notes that one of the most powerful sources of self-efficacy is mastery experience.

Mastery experience occurs when a child evaluates his or her own competence after learning and believes their efforts have been successful. Mastery experiences increase confidence and willingness to try similar and more challenging tasks. In addition, studies have also found that social experiences play a powerful role in the development of self-efficacy. The beliefs and behaviours held by teachers and peers are important in building the self-efficacy of all children in the classroom.

2.1. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 Paradigm of the study

The study is grounded on the premise that a student's level of reading comprehension has a significant impact on their academic performance. It posits that the ability to understand, interpret, and analyze written texts directly influences how students perform across different subjects in Senior High School. In this framework, reading comprehension serves as the independent variable, while academic performance, measured through the General Weighted Average (GWA), is considered the dependent variable.

The conceptual model illustrates the hypothesized relationship between these two variables. It suggests that students with higher reading comprehension skills are more likely to achieve better academic outcomes because they can efficiently process information, understand complex instructions, and critically evaluate learning materials. Conversely, students with lower reading comprehension may struggle to grasp essential concepts, which could negatively affect their academic performance.

Figure 1 presents the conceptual model of the study, which will guide the analysis and interpretation of the relationship between reading comprehension and academic performance of Grade 12 Senior High School students of San Miguel National High School, San Miguel, Bulacan, during School Year 2022–2023. This model emphasizes the importance of developing reading comprehension skills as a foundation for academic success and serves as the theoretical basis for the research hypotheses.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Design

The researchers used a quantitative method, particularly, the researcher used correlational research design. Quantitative methods emphasize objective measurements and the statistical, mathematical, or numerical analysis of data collected through polls, questionnaires, and surveys, or by manipulating pre-existing statistical data using computational techniques. Quantitative research focuses on gathering numerical data and generalizing it across groups of people or to explain a particular phenomenon (Babbie, 2010). The said research was used by the researchers to describe the relationships of the given variables. Moreover, a research instrument was used to identify the level of the students reading comprehension while the academic performance of the students was determined using their General Average from the last quarter. The researchers used a quantitative research design, particularly a correlational study. The researchers utilized correlational methods in this study. Correlational research is a type of non-experimental

research method in which a researcher measures two variables, understands and assesses the statistical relationship between them with no influence from any extraneous variable (Adams, 2019).

This research design was utilized in order to determine the relationship Reading Comprehension Levels and Academic Performance of Grade 12 students by describing them quantitatively.

3.2. Participants of the Study

The respondents of the study consisted of 258 Grade 12 Senior High School students of San Miguel National High School, San Miguel, Bulacan, who were officially enrolled during School Year 2022–2023. The participants were drawn from the different academic strands offered by the Senior High School program of the institution, ensuring representation across various fields of specialization. These strands include programs designed to prepare learners for higher education, employment, and skills development. The selection of respondents from diverse academic strands provided a comprehensive view of students' reading comprehension levels and academic performance, regardless of their chosen track. The Grade 12 students were specifically chosen because they are in the culminating year of Senior High School and are expected to have developed the necessary reading comprehension skills required for advanced academic tasks and future educational or career pursuits.

3.3. Research Locale

The study was conducted at San Miguel National High School, a public secondary school situated in the municipality of San Miguel, Bulacan. The school offers Senior High School education in accordance with the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum mandated by the Department of Education. As an academic institution serving learners from diverse backgrounds, San Miguel National High School provides various academic strands designed to equip students with the knowledge and skills necessary for higher education, employment, and lifelong learning. The school was selected as the research locale due to its accessibility to the researchers and its relevance to the objectives of the study, particularly in examining the reading comprehension levels and academic performance of Grade 12 Senior High School students.

3.4. Sampling Procedure

The researchers initially identified the total population of Grade 12 Senior High School students of San Miguel National High School, San Miguel, Bulacan, who were officially enrolled during School Year 2022–2023. Based on the school's official enrollment records, the total population consisted of 731 Grade 12 students across different academic strands. Since it was impractical to include the entire population in the study, a representative sample was determined to ensure the feasibility of data collection while maintaining the accuracy and generalizability of the results.

To determine the appropriate sample size, Slovin's formula was utilized. This formula is commonly used in educational research to calculate sample size when the population is known and when a specific margin of error is desired. By applying Slovin's formula, the researchers computed a sample size of 258 respondents, which was deemed sufficient to represent the total population of Grade 12 students and to yield reliable statistical results.

After determining the sample size, the researchers employed a Simple Random Sampling Technique to select the participants. Simple random sampling is a probability sampling method in which every individual in the population has an equal and independent chance of being chosen as part of the sample. This technique minimizes selection bias and ensures that the sample is representative of the population. According to Easton and McColl (n.d.), simple random sampling allows every possible sample of a given size to have an equal probability of selection, thereby enhancing the credibility and validity of the research findings.

The list of Grade 12 students was obtained from the school administration and served as the sampling frame. Each student was assigned a unique identification number, and the required number of respondents was selected randomly using a random selection process. This procedure ensured that the selection of participants was conducted in a fair, objective, and systematic manner, without favoring any specific group, section, or academic strand.

The use of Slovin's formula in combination with simple random sampling strengthened the methodological rigor of the study. These procedures ensured that the respondents adequately represented the Grade 12 student population of San Miguel National High School and that the results of the study could be confidently used in analyzing the relationship between reading comprehension and academic performance.

3.5. Research Instrument

This study adapted a Reading Questionnaire which consists of a 40-item Reading Comprehension Test formulated by Tran Hung (n.d). The survey question is divided into two sections; the first section of the questionnaire is consisting of five stories with 4-item questions. The second section of the questionnaire is five stories, for the first and section story consist of 5-item questions and the third to fifth story consists of 4-item questions.

The said instrument was used to determine the level of the student’s comprehension level. Lastly, the academic performance of students will represent by the students’ general weighted average.

3.6. Data Gathering Techniques

Before conducting the study, the researchers submit a permission letter to the principal of San Miguel National High School. After the permission letter was approved, the researcher will start to gather the data by giving a survey questionnaire to the chosen respondents. Before distributing the survey questionnaires, the researcher will greet and ask for the participants’ consent. Upon receiving the respondent’s consent, the researcher will proceed to orient the participants of the details, as well as the purpose and significance of the study. The researcher will personally administer the instrument to the respondents by hand. The participants are allowed enough time to analyze and answer the survey questionnaires. After they finished answering the survey questionnaires, the researcher will collect it from the participants.

The researcher will repeat the same procedure for the student respondents.

3.7. Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

The responses of the participants to the survey questionnaire were tallied and encoded by the researchers using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences software version 22.

The researchers made use of Likert-scale to interpret the gathered data. It was used in order to measure students’ level of reading comprehension.

Mean Range interpretation for reading comprehension		
Point	Scale	Interpretation
31-40	3.25-4.00	Very High Level of Reading Comprehension
21-30	2.50-3.34	High Level of Reading Comprehension
11-20	1.75-2.49	Low Level of Reading Comprehension
1-10	1.00-1.74	Very Low Level of Reading Comprehension

Mean Range interpretation for academic performance to interpret the values acquired for the correlation of two variables, Pearson Product Moment Correlation of Coefficient (Pearson R)

Pearson r Correlation Coefficient Interpretation Scale

Pearson r	Interpretation	
±0.80 to ±1.00	±0.80 to ±1.00	Very strong correlation
	±0.60 to ± 0.79	Strong correlation
	±0.40 to ± 0.59	Moderate correlation
	±0.20 to ±0.39	Weak correlation
	0.00 to ± 0.19	Very weak correlation

To interpret the gather data, the researchers used the following:

- Frequency and percentage were used to describe the demographic profile of the students.

- Mean and Standard Deviation was used to determine the level of Reading Comprehension and Academic Performance of the Students.
- Pearson Product Moment Correlation of Coefficient (Pearson R) was used to determine if Reading Comprehension is significantly related to the Academic Performance

4. Results and Discussions

This chapter shows the interpretation of the gathered data from the online survey questionnaires. This answers the given statement of the problem.

Table 1 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Female	166	64
Male	92	36
Total	258	100

The table shows the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their gender. Among the 258 respondents, 166 (64%) are females and 92 (36%) are males.

Table 2 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Strand

Strand	Frequency	Percentage (%)
ACCESS	88	34
ENGTECH	86	33
GENCAD	44	17
SOCSCI	40	16
Total	258	100%

The table shows the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their strand. Among the 258 respondents, 88 (34%) are from the Accountancy and Business strand, 86 (33%) are from the Engineering and Technology strand, 44 (17%) of the participants came from the General Academics strand and 40 (16%) are from the Social Sciences strand.

Table 3 Mean and Standard Deviation Interpretation for the Academic Performance

	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Academic Performance	258	92.05	3.68	Very High

The table shows the percentage of the academic performance of the students (M= 92.05, N= 258 and SD= 3.68) in Baliuag University Grade 12 Senior High School. The result suggests that most of the respondents are outstanding.

Table 4 Mean and Standard Deviation Interpretation for the Respondents' Reading Comprehension

	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Reading Comprehension	258	22.79	2.43	

The table presents the percentage of students' level of reading comprehension ($M= 22.79$, $N= 258$ and $SD= 2.43$) in Baliuag University Grade 12 Senior High School. The results suggest that the most of the respondents has high level of reading comprehension.

Table 5 Pearson 'R product-moment coefficient for Reading Comprehension and Academic Performance

Variable	Statistical Treatment	Academic Performance
Reading Comprehension	Pearson Correlation	0.355
	Sig.	0.001
	N	258

A Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was used to identify if there is an existing relationship between reading comprehension and the academic performance. The result showed that there is a weak positive relationship significant correlation between reading comprehension and the academic performance of the students, $r = .355$, $N = 258$, $p = .001$. Therefore, when the Reading Comprehension of the students increases their Academic Performance also increases. This is conclusive because we have to find a weak positive relationship. In addition, Chege (2012) indicated that reading comprehension is linked to academic achievement in the subjects studied, according to the report, and is therefore a consideration to consider when attempting to improve our students' academic performance. The intellect of a student can be a good predictor of his reading comprehension capacity.

4.1. Summary

This primary objective of this study entitled "Reading Comprehension and Academic Performance" is to determine the relationship of student's reading comprehension and academic performance. This study was conducted in San Miguel National High School Senior High School Department specifically grade 12 students. The researchers used correlational research design in order to determine the relationship between Reading Comprehension and Academic Performance. According to Tan (2014) stated that the aim of correlational analysis is to find connections between two or more variables. Simply stated, it looks to see if an increase or decrease in one variable causes an increase or decrease in another. Researchers may use the results of a correlational analysis to assess whether or not two variable shifts together, and to what extent.

The result of this study shows that there is a significant relationship between the reading comprehension and academic performance of the students, and it is supported by the study of Hijazi (2018) stated that as an outcome, as students' reading comprehension abilities develop, so will their learning competences and achievement, which will have a positive impact on their overall performance and academic success.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results and discussion of the study, the following conclusions are provided:

- The students have (high level of) Reading Comprehension.
- The students have outstanding Academic Performance.
- Reading comprehension is significantly related to the academic performance of the students, therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Recommendation

Considering that the study identified the academic performance through the reading comprehension skills of each student are not significantly correlated to the students' academic excellence, the following recommendations are suggested:

- For the students, they should read more books. The researchers also propose that students need to develop a habit of reading to help them achieve a high level of reading comprehension.
- For the teacher, they should give activities that will enhance the student's ability to learn and comprehend what they are reading.
- For the parents, they should be more involve in their child's academic performance, they should be more supportive on their child's needs regarding on enhancing their reading comprehension skills.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The researcher hereby declares that there is no conflict of interest, whether financial, professional, or personal, that could have influenced the conduct, analysis, or presentation of this research. The study was carried out with full integrity, objectivity, and adherence to ethical research standards. Any sources of information, assistance, or support relevant to the study have been properly acknowledged.

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Statement of Ethical Approval

This research was conducted in accordance with established ethical standards and guidelines. Ethical approval to conduct the study was obtained from the appropriate authority prior to the implementation of the research. All participants were properly informed about the purpose of the study, and their voluntary participation was secured through informed consent. Confidentiality and anonymity of the participants were strictly maintained, and all data gathered were used solely for academic and research purposes.

References

- [1] Abdullah, M. (2018). Reading Speed and Comprehension Enhancement in Hybrid Learning Delivery Mode. *Advances in Language and Literary Studies*, 9(3), 25–33. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=EJ1185882&site=ehost-live>
- [2] Awada, G., & Plana, M. G.-C. (2018). Multiple Strategies Approach and EFL Reading Comprehension of Learners with Dyslexia: Teachers' Perceptions. *International Journal of Instruction*, 11(3), 463–476. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=EJ1183378&site=ehost-live>
- [3] Biyik, M. A., Erdogan, T., & Yildiz, M. (2017). The Examining Reading Motivation of Primary Students in the Terms of Some Variables. *International Journal of Progressive Education*, 13(3), 31–49. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=EJ1159916&site=ehost-live>
- [4] Carroll, J. M., & Fox, A. C. (2017). Reading Self-Efficacy Predicts Word Reading But Not Comprehension in Both Girls and Boys. *Frontiers in psychology*, 7, 2056. doi:10.3389/fpsyg.2016.02056
- [5] Chege, E. W. (2012). Reading comprehension and its relationship with academic performance among standard eight pupils in rural Machakos (Unpublished Doctoral dissertation, Kenyatta University).
- [6] Chege, E. W. (2012). Reading comprehension and its relationship with academic performance among standard eight pupils in rural Machakos (Unpublished Doctoral dissertation, Kenyatta University)
- [7] Chege E. (2012). Reading Comprehension and its Relationship with Academic Performance Among Standard Eight Pupils in Rural Machakos (Unpublished Doctoral dissertation, Kenyatta University). Retrieved from <https://ir-library.ku.ac.ke/handle/123456789/3722#:~:text=The%20study%20concluded%20that%20reading,of%20hi s%20reading%20comprehension%20ability>.
- [8] Chrysos, M. (2017). Measuring Literary Reading Motivation: Questionnaires Design and Pilot Testing. *European Journal of Educational Research*, 6(4), 419–431. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=EJ1158553&site=ehost-live>
- [9] Erlidawati, & SyarfunI. (2018). The Effect of Cooperative Integrated Reading and Composition on Reading Comprehension of IAIN Lhokseumawe, Indonesia. *Advances in Language and Literary Studies*, 9(4), 153–160. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=EJ1190527&site=ehost-live>

- [10] Hijazi, Dima. (2018). The Relationship Between Students' Reading Comprehension and Their Achievement in English. *US-China Foreign Language*, 16, 10.17265/1539-8080/2018.03.002. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324915696_The_Relationship_Between_Students'_Reading_Compr_ension_and_Their_Achievement_in_English
- [11] Karahan, B. Ü. (2017). The Correlation of Reading Motivation & Reading Engagement with Reading Comprehension Skills in 8th Graders. *Online Submission*, 3, 3. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=ED580824&site=ehost-live>
- [12] Kung, F.-W. (2019). Teaching Second Language Reading Comprehension: The Effects of Classroom Materials and Reading Strategy Use. *Innovation in Language Learning and Teaching*, 13(1), 93-104. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=EJ1201144&site=ehost-live>
- [13] Kusdemir, Y., & Bulut, P. (2018). The Relationship between Elementary School Students' Reading Comprehension and Reading Motivation. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 6(12), 97-110. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=EJ1194556&site=ehost-live>
- [14] Meniado, J. C. (2016). Metacognitive Reading Strategies, Motivation, and Reading Comprehension Performance of Saudi EFL Students. *English Language Teaching*, 9(3), 117-129. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=EJ1095593&site=ehost-live>
- [15] Navaie, L. A. (2018). The Effects of Reciprocal Teaching on Reading Comprehension of Iranian EFL Learners. *Advances in Language and Literary Studies*, 9(4), 26-30. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=EJ1190529&site=ehost-live>
- [16] Özyeter, N. T., & Kutlu, Ö. (2018). Identifying the Relationships between Response Behaviors for Reading Comprehension Items and Student Characteristics. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 6(10), 148-157. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=EJ1191050&site=ehost-live>
- [17] Prawita, W., Prayitno, B. A., & Sugiyarto. (2019). Effectiveness of a Generative Learning-Based Biology Module to Improve the Analytical Thinking Skills of the Students with High and Low Reading Motivation. *International Journal of Instruction*, 12(1), 1459-1476. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=EJ1201245&site=ehost-live>
- [18] Ross, N. H. (2018). Sparking Reading Motivation with the Bluestem: School Librarians' Role with a Children's Choice Award. *School Library Research*, 21. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=EJ1202939&site=ehost-live>
- [19] Smith, A., & Feng, J. (2018). *Literature Circle and Gifted Students: Boosting Reading Motivation and Performance. Online Submission. Online Submission.* Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=ED588790&site=ehost-live>
- [20] Spencer, M., Wagner, R. K., & Petscher, Y. (2019). The Reading Comprehension and Vocabulary Knowledge of Children with Poor Reading Comprehension Despite Adequate Decoding: Evidence from a Regression-Based Matching Approach. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 111(1), 1-14. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=EJ1201282&site=ehost-live>
- [21] Tan, L. (2014). Correlational study. In W. F. Thompson (Ed.), *Music in the social and behavioral sciences: An encyclopedia* (pp. 269-271). Thousand Oaks: SAGE Publications. Retrieved from <https://repository.nie.edu.sg/bitstream/10497/18115/4/BC-MSB-2014-269.pdf>.
- [22] Vaknin-Nusbaum, V., Nevo, E., Brande, S., & Gambrell, L. (2018). Developmental Aspects of Reading Motivation and Reading Achievement among Second Grade Low Achievers and Typical Readers. *Journal of Research in Reading*, 41(3), 438-454. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=EJ1184590&site=ehost-live>
- [23] VanAken, Annette, "Effect of Ebooks on Reading Level, Reading Behaviors, and Attitude of Second Grade Students" (2014). *Doctoral Dissertations and Projects*. 956. <https://digitalcommons.liberty.edu/doctoral/956>
- [24] Yang, G., Badri, M., Al Rashedi, A., & Almazroui, K. (2018). The Role of Reading Motivation, Self-Efficacy, and Home Influence in Students' Literacy Achievement: A Preliminary Examination of Fourth Graders in Abu Dhabi. *Large-Scale Assessments in Education*, 6. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=EJ1192215&site=ehost-live>

- [25] Yau, J. C., & Lee, P. (2018). Achievement Differences and Gender Gaps in Reading Motivation: An Examination of Taiwanese Adolescent Readers of English as a Foreign Language. *Taiwan Journal of TESOL*, 15(1), 33–60. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=EJ1176533&site=ehost-live>